

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B240
Date: 24th August 2006
Take Off: 15:16:19
Landing: 19:36:45
Flight Time: 4h20m26

Campaign: DODO

Operating Area: Dakar to W

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Ellie Highwood	Reading University
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	CCM2 / AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
7	SWS	Clare McConnell	Met Office
8	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM
9	WAS / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University
10	Filters / PSAP	Paola Formenti	University of Paris 12 (LISA)
11	GRIMM	Paul Williams	Manchester University
12	Mission 2	Jim Haywood	Met Office
13	Mission Training	Clare Allen	Leeds University
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B240 Track 24-AUG-06

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b240
 Date: 24/08/06
 Project: DODO
 Location: North of DAKAR

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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150429		engines start	0.22 kft	334	
150818		inu to nav	0.22 kft	337	
150823		taxy	0.22 kft	344	
151600	154006	Profile 1	0.24 - 21.0 kft	352	
151619		T/O	0.22 kft	353	from Dakar
152741		Profile 1	11.0 kft	022	interrupt
152919		Profile 1	11.0 kft	022	resume
154006	161702	Run 1	21.0 kft	027	
154050		Sonde 1	21.0 kft	027	
154118		bbr	21.0 kft	027	shutter up (U)
154805		jw nevz zero	21.0 kft	353	
161054		Sonde 2	21.0 kft	008	
161702	165417	Profile 2	21.0 - 0.29 kft	007	
162255		bbr	16.1 kft	321	shutter down (D)
162326		bbr	15.6 kft	317	U
163126		Profile 2	8.5 kft	309	interrupt
164059		Profile 2	8.5 kft	133	resume
164139		bbr	8.0 kft	132	shuts discount (JH)
164545		Profile 2	4.6 kft	134	interrupt
164813		Profile 2	4.6 kft	302	resume
165258		Profile 2	0.94 kft	317	500ft/min
165417	170416	Run 2	0.29 - 0.27 kft	316	
170425	171333	Profile 3	0.31 - 5.0 kft	314	3
170609		qnh	1.3 kft	319	1009
172536	172851	Profile 4	5.0 - 2.6 kft	110	
172936	174417	Profile 5	2.6 - 12.0 kft	109	
170000	173600	PSAP	7.3 kft	109	stop logging
174556	181649	Profile 6	12.0 - 5.7 kft	185	
175241		Profile 6	6.0 kft	156	interrupt
180522		Profile 6	6.0 kft	152	resume
180743		Profile 6	4.1 kft	152	interrupt
181320		Profile 6	4.1 kft	341	resume
181649		Profile 6	1.1 kft	020	real end
181649	182716	Run 3	1.2 kft	019	
182717	183315	Profile 7	1.2 - 6.5 kft	348	
183454	184505	Run 4	6.5 kft	157	
184505	190000	Profile 8	6.5 - 22.0 kft	161	
184000	184400	PSAP	12.4 kft	188	stopped loggig
193645		Land	0.23 kft	349	At Dakar

B240 Track 24-AUG-06

FAAM Sortie Brief

DODO2: in-situ sampling and radiometric measurements of mineral dust

Flight No: B240

Date: 24 August 2006

Trial objectives:

To carry out in-situ sampling of mineral dust and measure the radiative effects over the ocean.

Location:

Over ocean areas off the coast of Senegal/Mauritania. N1830W1640

Weather:

High loadings of dust. Cloudless skies preferred.

Special requirements:

Low-level (50ft) flying over ocean.

60 degree banked orbits at 1000ft.

2 dropsondes required.

Flight pattern:

1. Take off from Dakar at 1530Z.
2. Profile ascent to FL220 towards [25mins, T=25]
3. Dropsonde at FL220
4. SLR at FL220 for ~20 minutes towards N1830W1640 [20mins, T=45]
5. Dropsonde at N1830W1640 at FL220
6. Profile descent to MPA (100ft), 1000ft/min above 3000ft, 500ft/min below 3000ft [25min, T=70]
7. Reciprocal turn and SLR at MPA (100ft) for 25 minutes [25mins, T=95]
8. Ascend to ~1000ft (over and above the sea-salt dominated layer), then SLR for 25 minutes [25mins, T=120]
9. Reciprocal turn and profile ascent to a level determined by the mission scientist [10mins, T=130]
10. Set of two in-situ sampling SLRs at different altitudes each run of 15minute duration [50mins, T=180]
11. Reciprocal turn and profile ascent to FL200 (or above the dust layer) [10mins, T=190]
12. SLR for 20mins [20mins, T=210]
13. Descent towards Dakar [20mins, T=230mins].
14. Land in Dakar [T=240mins].

Sortie Debrief B240 Mapping coastal dust to north

Flight Number: B240

Date: 24th August 2006

Mission: Ellie Highwood

Sortie Objectives: Mapping of dust in-situ to north of Dakar (for comparison with B239 to south). Radiation work in gap between encroaching cirrus and cloud streets.

Operating area:

Over ocean area off the Senegal and Mauritania coast, originally up to 18,30N, 1640W. Coastal region between Nouadibhou and Nouackchott.

Weather: Cloud throughout southern part of area and to east and west. Small cloud free region found over ocean.

Flight Patterns:

Profile from Dakar take off at ~1530 showed cloud between 1200ft and 3000ft. Some haze (neph 30Mm-1) above cloud. No sign of previously observed layer at FL065. Cirrus above the profile. CuNbs to east mark encroaching convection line. Cloud to west also. A SLR at FL210 is unlikely to be useful for radiation work due to cloud contamination. Towards the end of the run the cirrus did decrease and a radiative effect of around 60Wm⁻² was observed. A profile descent to 100ft showed moderate dust between FL150 and FL080 below which there was a clear blue slot. Some indication of non spherical particles at FL045. Sea state was around 3 with lots of whitcaps.

Having found very little dust, the sortie brief was abandoned and a profile to FL050 was carried out towards the coast. A sawtooth pattern was then begun towards the coast and then proceeding south along it. During this, layers were observed at 3500ft and FL050. PSAP had a logging problem for part of this flight. The top of the sawtooth was at FL120. Much air traffic control manouvering was necessary on the descent down around Nouackchott. Dust was only found in any great quantity at around 1000ft along the coast line so an SLR was carried out following the coastline. (Note this would be good to compare with B173). The nephelometer maximum was only 80 Mm-1. A further profile ascent was followed by an in-situ sampling run at FL065 where relatively little dust was found. A final profile climb was made to FL220 before returning to Dakar.

Summary:

A frustrating in-situ flight with little opportunity for radiation. Some radiative work at northern most end but little dust compared to previous flights. What dust was present was in patchy and very thin layers that made in-situ work very difficult. Consistent with findings to the south in B239 too.

Problems

SWS intermittent

Lower SHIMs has a shutter problem allowing only one module at a time.

Lower pyrgeometer still not working.

Neph needs calibrating? Blue scattering is very low all the time.

PSAP stopped logging for part of the run.

Flow rates may need re-calibration on neph and psap.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.240** Date **24/8/06** Name **ELLIE, HIGHWOOD** age **1** of **3**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
T/O					$\Sigma T = 29.0$, Some haze, considerable cloud
151600	P1 \uparrow	FL100	\rightarrow BIKIS		Haze, cloud base 1200ft cloud top 3000ft. Haze, dust? above cloud 5000ft/minute
		FL100			Neph below only $\approx 30 m^{-1}$
152741	P110	FL100			Profile interrupt, air traffic to Dust seen earlier in day @ FL085 now disappeared. AOD ≈ 0.2
152947	P1	FL100			P1 resumed. Ci above. Mid level cloud base ^{very thin} @ FL150 Neph to zero above this Cloud extensive. Cbs to east Cirrus looks less to north, consistent with forecast.
154006	Amend R1 stat	FL210			End profile start run. Sonde drop Mid level cloud \uparrow to east and being blown towards us. No radiation work this run
161054	R1	FL210			Sonde 2
161702	R1/p2	FL210 \downarrow			End run Radiative effect $60 W m^{-2}$ Good at end of run.
161702	P2	FL210 \downarrow			Some haze @ FL150. Can't see any Ci SWS not working. SHIMS Clear below? $\Delta F \downarrow$ Haze stats at 15 $\&$
163126		FL085			P interrupt to turn Bottom of dust is about 8000ft- can see clear blue slab.

FLO10
2000ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.240** Date 24/8/06 Name ELLIE; HIGHWOOD age 2 of 3.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
164059	P2	FLO85↓			Profile recommenced
164540	P2	FLO45			Profile interrupt, non spherical particles
164813	P2↓	FLO45			Profile recommenced Clearstbt visible and in neph
					↑ dust, ↓ O ₃ @
	P2	100ft			Seastate 3-4 end profile
165417	R2				lots of whitecaps, heinann.
170416	P3↑	100ft to 2500ft.		away from point A	500ft/min Cu to west
					Ships steaming on LHS, AH
171333	P3	FLO50			Profile interrupt.
172536	P4	FLO50↓			Profile descent
	P4	FLO 2500ft.			
	P5↑				500ft/min small layer @ 3500ft.
					Big layer FLO50
					PSAP logging problem
172936	P5	FL120			End profile
174556	P6	FL120↓			Star profile
175241	P6	FLO60			interrupt ATC. Haze below us.
					Much manoeuvring!!!
180522	P6	FLO60↓			Reconnaissance profile
	P6	FLO40			Interrupt
181321	P6	FLO40 → 1000ft			Resume
181649	P6				End
181711	R3	1000ft			Run in bottom dust layer 80m ⁻¹
					Along coastline

saw tracks towards coast when along it

down 10 up 5
up 5 SLR2 15
SLR1 15 up 10 → home

GMT	Run/P	Height	heading	GPS	Remarks
182716	R3 end P7 stat	1000ft ↑	346		End run / stat profile 1000ft/min
183315	P7 end	FL065	161		
183454	R4	FL065	161		Stat run
184505	P8	FL065			Multiple cloud layers ^{wide} at
190000	P8 end	FL220			high End profile, end science
	Go home	→	too long a flight		
		FL170			Cloud top.

t/o 15:16
land 19:36

4hr 20

4hr 10

8hr 30

Check 0000 flying hours.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B240	Date	24/8/06	Operator(s)	C-McCONNELL	log page	1	of	2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

SWS

150455			GF	15	75	Dark			
150521						Rec - on ground. ZENITH			
151619	T/O								
152818						Dark			
152831						Rec			
						Restart SWS			
153202			GF	50	100	Dark			
153221						Rec			
153253				200	250	Dark			
153309						Rec			
153435						Dark			
						Restart SWS			
153659				150	200	Dark			
153710						Rec			
154020				150	200	Dark			
154053			174A	150	200	Rec - NADIR			
154816				200	350	Dark			
154841						Rec			
155618				100	350	Dark			
155630						Rec			
150466						Dark			
160610				75	250	Dark			
160655						Rec			
160819						Dark			
160836						Rec			
161106				100	350	Dark			
161117						Rec			
161256						Dark			
161418				100	350	Dark - false			
161436						Dark - OK			
161446						Rec			
161549						Dark			
161731			GF	100	350	Dark			
161756						Rec ZENITH			
161818						Dark			
161833						Rec - no signal at all			
162132						Dark			
162145						Rec			
1622						Single shutter			
162547						Dark			
162603						Rec			
162628				250	500	Dark			
162643						Rec			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight # **B240** Date **24/8/06** Operator(s) **C. MCCONNELL** log page **2** of **2**

Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

SWS

163033			BF	250	500	Dark
163307						Dark
163320						Rec
165301						Dark
165226				250	500	Dark
165443						Rec - NIR only still
165417	R2					
170647						Dark
170807				250	500	Dark
170820	P3					Rec
171608						Dark
171738				250	500	Dark - false
171753						Dark - OK
171808						Rec
174035						Dark
174068						Rec
174128				350	750	Dark
174205	P5					Rec
1743						odd VIS signals
175255				200	400	Dark
175514						Rec
181057				350	750	Dark
181116	P6					Rec
1819						VIS Signal appeared. T=2200
182507						Dark
182526	R3					Rec
183636						Dark
183649						Rec
184502						Dark
184517	R4					Rec
184952				350	1000	Dark
185010						Rec
185249				500	1000	Dark
185314						Rec
190525						Dark
190540						Rec
190800				500	2000	Dark
190828						Rec
191018						Dark - false
191043						Dark - OK
						End due to high solar zenith angle.

SHIMS

SHIMS SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET						
Flight #	B910	Date	24/8/06	Operator(s)	C. MCCONNELL	log page 1 of 2
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks
				Vis	NIR	

SHIMS

						Clock set.
151619	T10					USH
152725				50	100	Dark
152741						Rec - USH
1529						SHIMS switched off.
153052				50	100	Dark
153108						Rec
153532						Dark
						Restart SHIMS
153938				50	100	Dark
153954						Rec.
154124						Dark
	LSH					
154224				200	300	Dark - false
154246						Dark - OK
154306						Rec - LSH
154921				200	300	Dark
154941				300	300	Dark
155000						Rec
155221						Dark
155300						Rec - no VIS.
155439				300	300	Dark
155510						Rec
155531				200	200	Dark
155540						Rec
1555						Going thru cloud.
160554						Dark
160608						Rec
160949						Dark
161005						Dark Rec - NIR
161030						Dark VIS
161043						Rec
161923						Dark
161942						Rec - no sig.
162331						Dark
162332						Rec
162514						Dark
162526						Rec
163135				350	200	Dark
163150						Rec
163233						Dark
163243						Rec

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B240**

Date: 24 August 06

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU	Y	Y	<u>Probes</u>		
XR5M GPS	Y	y	FFSSP	Y	N
Cruciform GPS	Y	Y	PCASP	Y	Y
Satcom C	Y	Y	2D-P	Y	Y
Satcom H	Y	Y	2D-C	Y	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	
De-Iced Temp	Y	Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	Y	SID 2	N	
Heimann	Y	Y	HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	N	
G. Eastern	Y	Y	CIP100	N	
J. Williams	Y	Y			
Nevzorov	Y	Y			
TWC	N				
FWVS	N		<u>Racks:</u>		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC	N	
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	N	
“ IR	Y	Y			
“ SHIMS	y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	Y
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	Y	Y
“ IR	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ SHIMS	Y	Y	AMS	Y	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	Y	Y	2BT O3	N	
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	N	
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	N	
SO2	Y	N	Formaldehyde	N	
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	N	
CO	Y	Y	CPI	N	
ORAC	N		NOxy	N	
PAN	Y	Y	PTRMS	N	
PERCA	N		Bag Sampling	N	
WAS	Y	Y	Tube Sampling	N	

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B240

Date: 24 August 2006

Instruments

Muck in Ffc requires window to be removed

Lower bbr(ir) u/s and no spare.

PSAP data logging repeatedly stopped and had to be restarted. No reason could be found.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B240:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	Awaiting processing completion
PSAP	No log appears to have been taken for this flight
Filters	Awaiting completed log
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
GRIMM	No log currently available
WAS	No log currently available

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Upward Facing Cameras
3 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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